

Sustainability Education for Human Capital Development in Higher Learning Institutions in Rwanda

Regine Uwihirwe

Lecturer, Accounting and Finance, School of Business Management and Economics, University of Kigali, Rwanda

Stephen Kimuya

Lecturer, Accounting and Finance, School of Business Management and Economics, University of Kigali, Rwanda

Kung'u Gabriel Kamau

Lecturer, Accounting and Finance, School of Business Management and Economics, University of Kigali, Rwanda

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Abstract:

Vision 2050 envisage Rwanda as a high-income country with improved living standards for all Rwandans. One of the main pillars to help Rwanda achieve this ambition is building a strong education system that is able to develop human capital needed to fill the skill gap as required by the society and the industries. To achieve this, sustainability education could play a crucial role. This paper aims at investigating the effect of sustainability education on human capital development in Rwanda. Three key concepts of concern were identified in literature along which we built our discussions and analysis. These included, inclusive education (proxied by quality, equality and diversity in education), curriculum breadth (proxied by science and extra-curriculum activities) and industrial matching (proxied by skill transfer, meeting market needs and employability).

The paper is anchored on human capital and social capital theories. The primary data was collected from a random sample of 270 students in University of Kigali (UoK) and University of Rwanda- College of Business Gikondo Campus. The paper used PLS-SEM method to model the relationships among the study variables and analysed using SmartPLS4. We find positive and significant effect of sustainability education on the human capital development. The results have policy and practical implications going forward to the future. We suggest a holistic integration of sustainability mentality in the education system in order to grow suitable human capital ready for the market.

Keywords: Sustainability education, inclusive education, curriculum breadth, industrial matching, Rwanda.

Introduction

Vision 2050 envisage Rwanda as a high-income country with improved living standards for all Rwandans. One of the main pillars to help Rwanda achieve this ambition is building a strong education system that is able to develop human capital needed to fill the skill gap as required by the society and the industries. To

achieve this, sustainability education could play a crucial role, in value creation through an inclusive, diverse and quality education system. Sustainability education (education for sustainable development) aims at creating quality human life achieved through education that balances the effects of human actions on environment, society and economy. The

objective is to ensure that human interactions create human value through sustainable transfer of knowledge, that in itself promotes a sustainable coexistence. However, different educational systems across Africa have failed to integrate their curricula towards creating quality human life for this and future generation. The main challenge within the system is inability to provide linkage between what is learnt in classroom with what the society, the economy and the environment require. Our individual and community actions collectively impact on the ability to create a sustainable human capital, economic growth while at the same time preserving the environment for quality human life. Despite the efforts by government of Rwanda and other agencies, the education system has still failed to impart a positive and lasting impact on the learners' ability to appreciate the significance of what is learnt and the need for building a healthy society. In addition, there is a mismatch between what is learnt and what the society and the industry require for growth and development.

This calls for a paradigm shift to incorporate sustainability education in the curriculum, to impart long-lasting influence on the society in a way that builds human capital that smoothly transit from class to the society, environment and the economy. Sustainability education aims at value creation where quality human life is the main focus. Quality human life is attained when the three key pillars of sustainability, including the environment, the society and the economy are well integrated. The well-being of the nation can be achieved if there is sustainable education system that builds a healthy human capital, adequately skilled labour that is gainfully employed (Wilson & Stevenson, 2018). Recognizing the collective impact of our individual and community actions and activities on our ability to sustain and improve current living standards, the current generation should be empowered to cater for their needs while still concerned about the future generation. The education system should therefore aim to promote economic growth, social development, while conserving resources for the future and decreasing depletion rates, which is achievable

thorough sustainability education (Glavic, 2020). According to Leicht, *et al.*, (2018), sustainability education is highly needed and is emerging prominent among colleges and universities as part of their curricula, especially as tied to business and science.

As noted by Leicht, *et al.* (2018), there is need for a paradigm shift towards a sustainable future that can be addressed through fundamental changes in curriculum. The human capital should be proactive rather than reactive to challenges and become stewards of the resources. A quality education offers learners with the skills and capacities needed to become economically and socially productive. Different government and nongovernmental agencies have pointed out continuously that education is the tool for policy change and for long-life effect in positively changing the society. Education in this respect, refer to all learning process that imparts knowledge or skills to people. Consequently, any negative imbued or perceived misconceptions can either be reinforced in an education system or erased and transformed to new ideologies through education (Quendler & Lamb, 2016). These arguments recognize the role played by education in shaping human thinking, behaviour and perceptions of the environment, society and the world.

As pointed out by Fiselier, *et al.*, (2017), education plays a significant role in guiding the society towards sustainable future. It does this especially by shaping pupils and students into adults who will be conscious of their stance within the planet's system. Further, it helps instil in the learners' mind the need to be responsible in their lifestyle and therefore attempt to design society in a way that it will nurture a healthy human-nature relationship. Sustainability education empowers the individuals to become productive at work, to achieve self-awareness as well as become conscious about his/her social and physical environment (Njoku & Onyegbula, 2017). Therefore, having quality and inclusive education would help transform the community in such a way that the members are empowered to contribute to the socioeconomic development of the country. This study sought to assess the effect of sustainability education on

the human capital development in Rwanda. Three specific objectives were formulated as follows:

- 1) To assess the effect of inclusive education on the human capital development in Rwanda.
- 2) To analyse the effect of curriculum scope on the human capital development in Rwanda.
- 3) To assess the contribution of industrial matching curriculum on the human development in Rwanda.

Literature Review

Conceptual Building Blocks and Hypotheses Development

Among the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), SDG4 aims at ensuring inclusive and equitable education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all. In line with this SDG, sustainability education aims at promoting quality education that would impart skills and knowledge to the learner in such a way that the learner appreciates the call to maintain a balanced human and environmental ecosystem. Sustainability education is triggered by the need to promote social, economic and environmental balance for this generation and the future generation. Different authors have discussed the significance of sustainability education and the concepts underlying this approach to education. The Government of Rwanda (GoR) has also put efforts towards sustainability education with Rwanda Environmental Management Authority (RAMA) recognizing the impact of education on environmental shared responsibility (Nsanzimana & Tushabe, 2010).

According to Nousheen, *et al.*, (2020), sustainability education involves broadening the education system to incorporate in the curriculum the social, economic and environmental objectives. This aims at developing human capital that is conscious of the impact of human actions on the planet as a whole, and therefore take shared responsibility to preserve the ecology for the sake of the future generation. This education system considers the

long-term effects and concerns of today's actions to benefit the human society, but at the same time caring to preserve and maintain ecological balance. In addition, the system calls for retaining the natural capital intact, in such a way that the sources and sink functions of the environment should not be degraded. How this can be achieved is through a holistic approach to sustainability concepts and integrating the same into the education system. In this paper, we argue that the broad definition of sustainability applies, and therefore, propose three main areas in our conceptual framework. Namely, inclusive education, curriculum breadth and industrial matching. According to Lenglet, *et al.*, (2010), sustainability education is all about how through education and learning, individual, groups, organizations and communities can gain transferable skills and knowledge that aim at creating greater sustainability of their social, cultural, economic and environmental relations and values. Sustainability Education (SE) invites the learner as actors rather than consumers of education, to be actively engaged in the realities and challenges of life and transforming these realities in the perspective of greater social, economic and environmental sustainability.

As discussed by UNESCO, inclusive education should be part of an education system. In this discussion, inclusive education is concerned with identifying all barriers to education and removing them to enable all children and young adults to access quality education equitably (UNESCO, 2017). Through inclusive education, every learner matters and therefore should be exposed to similar education opportunities like his/her peers without discrimination (Mundial & UNICEF, 2016). Inclusive education provides equal learning opportunities to learners regardless of the gender, social/ethnic origin, religion, economic conditions, nationality or language. For this matter then, inclusive education may be seen to promote quality education that is available and accessible to all people. In line with SDG 4, UNESCO argues that achieving inclusivity in education calls upon different nations to revamp their education systems addressing all forms of exclusion and marginalization disparity and inequality in

accessing education. Further, the system should address issues to do with disparity in participation in education (UNESCO, 2017).

Moreover, Pather and Slee (2018) note that through inclusive education, different children or young adult are given equal opportunities to develop and shape their future career in discovering their potential economically and socially. The education also sharpens all learners equally empowering them to be self-reliant in their adult life. It is also through inclusive education that the learners acquire necessary skills to compete favourably in the labour market. Inclusivity in education requires acknowledging learners' diversity and integrating these by offering equal life-long learning opportunities in order to enhance and democratize the learning process for all students. It calls for attention to all forms of inequality in the access and participation to quality education for all. Traditionally, exclusion to education may be as a result of gender, ethnic background, religion, poverty, indigenous people, minority and people with special needs and disabilities. While these experiences bring about inequalities in the society, gender inequality is cited as the biggest challenge world over since it affects a bigger portion of the society in almost all countries (UNDP 2019). However, incorporating these people and tackling the barriers in the education system create learning opportunities for their development, and consequently empowering them by positioning them socially and economically in the community. We therefore proposed the first hypothesis as follows:

H_{A1}: There is a positive and significant effect of inclusive education on human capital development.

Further, sustainability education should include curriculum breadth and depth. The learning ecosystem, which according to Care and Anderson (2017) includes both the formal and informal education system, should be such that it is broad in its coverage. As per the mission statement of the Ministry of Education (MINEDUC), the purpose of the education ecosystem is to transform the learners into skilled human capital for socioeconomic

development of the individuals, the society and the country at large. This can be achieved through provision of quality education that is broad enough, promotes sciences, technology, and critical thinking (MINEDUC, 2020). Quality and sustainable education should lay emphasis on providing a broad range of skills necessary to shape the children, youths and the adults into responsible citizens (Care & Anderson, 2017). The changing demands for skilled workforce also put pressure on the need to focus on broad curriculum. In addition, curriculum breadth provides a wide range of subject coverage, skills development and avenues for identifying talents of the learners. These are all necessary to serve the wide range of industrial needs for different skilled human capital. Our second hypothesis was thus formulated:

H_{A2}: Curriculum scope positively and significantly impacts the human capital development.

The education system should be able to shape the human capital in such a way that it encounters the conceptual and ethical frameworks that address the need for sustainability. Human capital development thus becomes vital for the social and economic development of a nation. More specifically, the human capital is intangible and inimitable resource, and once developed can bring gainful results to the industry. Consequently, different authors such as Adedeji and Campbell, (2013) have pointed that the way forward in achieving sustainable development is by starting with developing positive attitudes and skilled human capital. Human capital development involves building and enlarging the human capabilities through education, on-job training and continuous skill development. This enhances the human potential at workplace increasing their working efficiency, productivity and consequently empowers them to compete favourably in the labour market. Through human capital development, a country can benefit greatly economically and socially (Adedeji & Campbell, 2013). Greater assets for nation building are the human resources. Obviously, education empowers learners to self-knowledge and their relationship with environment. It lays ground for their future such

that they become employable and fit smoothly in the marketplace. With sustainability education, the learners are provided skills that match the industrial needs, become competitive in the

labour market. We therefore formulated the third hypothesis thus:

H_{A3}: Industrial matching positively and significantly influences human capital development.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Empirical Studies

Empirical literature has evidenced the movement towards a more pragmatic approach to education with various disciplines advocating for the inclusion of learning skills that promotes all aspects of human life. For instance, on the significance of education in developing human capital, Adedeji and Campbell (2013) pointed out that higher education is a prerequisite for the production of highly competent employees. Kola-Olusanya (2013) demonstrate that sustainability studies can effectively be integrated in learning to have strong effect on the human capital development. In particular, the author shows that environmental sustainability can be oriented towards learning and development in a way that imbues a human capital is sensitive to corporate sustainability as well as environmental sustainability. Furthermore, economic development that gainfully seek for maximizing economic

production for the current generation without regards for the future generation would be detrimental to both the current and the future generations. Hence, in order to meet the current needs without compromising the needs of the future generations, sustainable development sets out to achieve a balance between economic, social and ecological objectives. This balance is based on the understanding that sustainable economic and social development is critically dependent on the health of the ecological system upon which this development is based.

Sharma and Kelly (2014) examined the perception of students on Education for sustainable Development (ESD) in the accounting and business curriculum in New Zealand. The findings showed that students perceived ESD as a good thing that improves their knowledge and responsibilities towards the ecology and society. Based on their findings, the authors find the need to bring more changes in

teaching sustainable development especially at university level. The empirical study by Green and Somerville (2015) focused on the teachers' ability to integrate SE within the already overcrowded curriculum. Their findings pointed out three main challenges of incorporating SE in primary schools in Australia, namely, i) the lack of skills among the teachers, ii) overcrowded curriculum such that it is difficult to add any new subjects and iii) the emergent nature of SE. Similarly, Verhulst and Lambrechts (2015) indicated in their study the barriers to integrating sustainability in higher learning education including i) lack of awareness about sustainability, ii) the structure of HE and iii) resource constraint.

Fiselier, *et al.*, (2017), collected data using structured questionnaire and interview and found that different institutes of higher learning in UK have fully integrated ESD in their curricula, while others have partially integrated the system. Some institutions, however, prefer to offer ESD separately as different courses designed around sustainability. These results clearly show that there is no single approach to sustainability education, but rather a multitude of approaches. Different institutions approach the same idea in different ways. However, there is consensus on the importance of having SE within the education system.

On the value of education to employability of the graduates, Storen and Aamodt (2010) conducted a comparative survey among graduates in thirteen different countries. The authors used the graduates' perceptions to gauge the usefulness and the quality of education offered at higher education institutions in these countries. Of interest, they concentrated on programme characteristics on the impact of obtaining and doing a job. The findings showed that programme characteristics influences the value of the programme in the labour market, but has low influence on the graduates obtaining a job. However, the graduate ability to do a job and maintain the job is significantly influenced by the programme characteristics. Donald, *et al.*, (2018) studied the university students' perceptions on how university education has prepared them to enter and compete in the

global market. Also of interest was the students' perceptions of the costs-benefits of the education where the authors investigated the costs incurred to acquire higher learning and the employment earnings or gains associated to the acquired education. Using qualitative method, data obtained through semi-structured interview showed that investment in HE offers a net financial gain. Again, as the graduate progress they feel more employable from a personal perspective but less from a market perspective because of competition in the labour market.

O'Neill and Bagchi-Sen (2023) investigated the relationship between higher learning institutions and human capital development in United States. The authors' interest was on the contribution of education offered by public universities on the skills development, graduate placement and retention at workplace. The research collected data from sixty-four universities and found that regional variation, the degree level and the study programme contribute significantly to the learners' development and employability.

Theoretical Framework

Human Capital Theory

This theory proposed by Garry Becker (1967) and Theodore Schultz (1988) postulate that human capital can be formed through different approaches that combine the innate abilities and investments in human beings (Adedeji & Campbell, 2013). Such investments include expenditure on education, training, health care and nutrition. Through these investments, the human capital can be developed to achieve greater capabilities required to tackle challenges of life and work demands. Through education, the human capital can be developed to increase efficiency and productive capacity required by the industries and the economy. Hence, investment in education is a key factor in the development of human capital. Just like other investments like in finance and in development projects, investments in education system can enhance the growth and development of human capital which in turn would increase the national

productivity and economic growth. Access to quality education provides technical and specialized skills, increases the marginal productivity of the workers and avails to the market personnel capable to drive organizations to success. This theory, therefore, shows the importance of education to the human capital development and the significance of this development towards the individuals and the society at large.

Further, the theory posits that human capital is not homogenous and through life experiences can be developed further to achieve more potential. It looks at the human capital as the economic value of an individual which through education, training and exposure can be shaped to tackle the life challenges. This implies that human beings can increase their level of productive capacity through higher education and skill-oriented training. As a consequence of this belief, developing the human capital is seen as the prerogative of every education geared to shaping the human beings ready to work within different professions and work-related demands. This theory therefore is consistent with this study inasmuch as it holds the value of education toward human capital development, in addition, higher education should shape the human capital increasing the shared responsibility for sustainable coexistence. In this study, we argued that sustainability education has the mandate to shape the learners by developing the capabilities while at the same imbuing in them the consciousness towards the society, the economy and the environment.

Social Capital Theory

Social capital theory, which can be traced back to Coleman (1988), posits that social relations and environments are essential factors wherein the human capital can develop. This theory holds that the development of human capital is more enhanced within environments where the social ties are strong and stable (Engbers, *et al.*, 2017). For example, stable family environment is seen as an enabling environment that supports the growth and development of human capital. Through such stable social environment, the goal of education towards human development

is enhanced. For effective human capital development, the social capital theory holds that human beings need both quality education as well as stable social environments including school, class, family, religious environments. The students' social learning environment matters when it comes to delivering quality and sustainable education. Therefore, in order to thrive, sustainability education should be offered within a stable and enabling social environment. Within education, social capital is relationship between the students, families, classmates, teachers and community available to support and motivate the students towards academic excellence.

This theory resonates well with the current study as it emphasizes the effect of the student learning environment towards achieving sustainability education and human capital development. The theory captures the needs to establish stable and enabling learning environments such as stable family, supporting and motivating teachers, favourable learning classrooms, good education policies as well as an elaborate curriculum. Similarly, the theory importantly stresses the needs for information exchange for human development. However, such information exchange thrives better where there are social networks and trust. Consequently, information exchange in an education setting thrives within social environments. In fact, high trust among individuals facilitates the exchange of more knowledge, therefore greatly influencing the development of human capital. Moreover, sustainability education calls for the learners to appreciate their responsibility towards the society, the environment and the economy for this generation and future generations. But this can be achieved if the learner also perceives that the society is supportive of this.

Methodology

To achieve the stated research objective, analytical research design was considered the most appropriate. It was also appropriate to test the hypotheses and to draw conclusions about the significance of sustainability education on

human capital development. The study targeted the higher learning institutions and solicited for responses from the learners in two institutions in Rwanda, namely University of Kigali and University of Rwanda- College of Business Gikondo Campus. The primary data was obtained using structured questionnaires distributed to the two randomly selected higher learning institutions. The participants were inducted during their class time, and they were given instructions on how to participate in this. They were free to participate or not. In addition, ethical issues were observed to ensure integrity of the information gathered as well as observing confidentiality needed. A random sample of 270 students participated and duly filled and returned the questionnaires. Data was analysed using Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Model PLS-SEM approach. To perform the SEM analysis, we used SmartPLS4 software credited for its ability in partial least square analysis (Ringle, *et al.*, 2022).

Results and Discussions

The findings are presented following the specific objectives and the hypotheses that were tested. We first conduct the model fit analysis using reliability validity and multicollinearity tests and then present the model in pictorial form to give a picture of the inner and out models for our tests. Lastly, we present and discuss the major outcomes of our model analysis using path coefficients, correlations and R². With these, then we were able to draw conclusion about our hypotheses whether to accept or reject.

SEM Model Analysis

According to Risher and Hair (2017), PLS-SEM model does not have stringent assumptions compared to the CB-SEM. Hence, we analysed the SEM model using the reliability, validity and multicollinearity tests. We tested the reliability and validity of the outer model (Table 1) and of the inner model (Table 2). In Table 1, we use the outer weights test for the reliability and validity of the outer model.

Table 1. Outer Model Reliability Test

Inclusive Education		Curriculum Scope		Industrial Matching	
	Outer weights		Outer weights		Outer weights
Q1 <- Quality	0.691	Q9 <- Science	0.371	Q17 <- Skills	0.339
Q6 <- Quality	0.569	Q10 <- Science	0.488	Q19 <- Skills	0.349
Q2 <- Equality	0.457	Q11 <- Science	0.470	Q20 <- Skills	0.367
Q3 <- Equality	0.326	Q12 <- Extra-Curriculum	0.386	Q22 <- Skills	0.378
Q7 <- Equality	0.653	Q13 <- Extra-Curriculum	0.353	Q21 <- Market Needs	0.500
Q4 <- Diversity	0.271	Q14 <- Extra-Curriculum	0.363	Q18 <- Market Needs	0.380
Q5 <- Diversity	0.615	Q15 <- Extra-Curriculum	0.333	Q23 <- Market Needs	0.413
Q8 <- Diversity	0.475	Q26 <- HCD	0.211	Q16 <- Employability	0.284
Q26 <- HCD	0.225	Q27 <- HCD	0.237	Q24 <- Employability	0.554
Q27 <- HCD	0.223	Q28 <- HCD	0.197	Q25 <- Employability	0.473
Q28 <- HCD	0.228	Q29 <- HCD	0.226	Q26 <- HCD	0.197
Q29 <- HCD	0.202	Q30 <- HCD	0.217	Q27 <- HCD	0.234
Q30 <- HCD	0.229	Q31 <- HCD	0.233	Q28 <- HCD	0.174
Q31 <- HCD	0.222	Q32 <- HCD	0.116	Q29 <- HCD	0.234
Q32 <- HCD	0.105			Q30 <- HCD	0.240
				Q31 <- HCD	0.244
				Q32 <- HCD	0.108

Source: Primary data (2023)

As stated by Ringle, *et al.*, (2022), the researcher has the freedom to pre-specify outer weights to initialize the PLS-SEM analysis based on previous researchers or empirical evidence. In

this case, we used the weight loadings to specify which observed variables had the most significant contribution to our reflective constructs.

Table 2. Construct Reliability Tests

Inclusive Education		Scope		Industrial Matching	
Quality	0.768	Science	0.791	Skills	0.791
Equality	0.711	Extra-Curriculum	0.790	Market Needs	0.815
Diversity	0.754	HCD	0.857	Employability	0.780
HCD	0.857			HCD	0.857

Source: Primary data (2023)

Table 2 reports the reflective construct reliability tests for our three SEM models. We used the composite reliability test among the observed indicators used for the constructs. According to Clark, *et al.*, (2021), constructs are said to be

reliable enough if the results of the composite reliability test is more than 0.7. In our case, all the constructs had reliability greater than the threshold, and therefore reliable enough to be included in the model.

Table 3. Multicollinearity Tests-Inner models

Inclusive Education		Curriculum Scope		Industrial Matching	
	VIF		VIF		VIF
Quality -> HCD	1.225	Science -> HCD	1.361	Skills -> HCD	1.866
Equality -> HCD	1.237	Extra-Curriculum -> HCD	1.361	Employability -> HCD	1.757
Diversity -> HCD	1.222			Market Needs -> HCD	1.852

Source: Primary data (2023)

Multicollinearity was tested using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). According to Tan, (2022), a VIF of less than 10 is considered an indication of absence of the problems of multicollinearity. As reported in Table 3, all our contracts had VIF of less than 10 and therefore no multicollinearity observed.

Effect of Inclusive Education on Human Capital Development

The structural equation model was formulated as shown in Figure 2. The outer models represent a total of eight surveyed items for inclusive education (labelled Q1-Q8) and seven surveyed items for human capital development (labelled

Q26-Q32). The inner model depicts our reflective constructs quality education, equality in education and diversity in education as proxies for inclusive education, on one hand, and human capital development on the other. To perform the SEM analysis, we used SmartPLS4™ software credited for its ability in partial least square analysis.

Figure 2 reports the pictorial presentation of the measurement models (outer models) and the structural model (inner model) while analysing the effect of inclusive education on the human capital development. In this study, inclusive education was analysed using three main

reflective constructs, namely the quality of education, the equality in education and the diversity in education. Quality, equality and diversity in education as reflective constructs were measured using statements given to the respondents. We argued in this model that

quality, equality and diversity in education improves the level of inclusive education which in turn leads to a holistic human capital development. The analyses of the model are provided in Table 4.

Figure 2: Structural Equation Model- Inclusive education on Human Capital Development (HCD)

Source: Primary data (2023)

Table 4. PLS-SEM Analyses for Inclusive Education

Path	Path coefficients	p-values	r	R ²	AdjR ²
Quality -> HCD	0.381	0.000	0.495		
Equality -> HCD	0.118	0.014	0.330	0.307	0.299
Diversity -> HCD	0.207	0.001	0.381		

Source: Primary data (2023)

The PLS-SEM analyses provided showed that all the path coefficients were statistically significant since their respective p-value were less than 5%. The three indicators contribute positively to the human capital development, but at varying rates or degree. The quality in the education system had the highest contribution of 0.381 with a correlation ($r=0.495$, $p<0.05$) bigger than the other variables. Having diversity in an education system to include all gender, low-income earning families and all cultures tend to play significant role in human capital development. The path

coefficient was positive at 0.207 with a significant correlation ($r=0.381$, $p<0.000$). Lastly, equality in education that includes people with disability and giving people equal learning opportunity had the least contribution. However, its path was positive at 0.118 and significant with $r=0.330$. The overall $R^2=0.307$ showed that inclusive education measured by quality, equality and diversity in education contributes 30.7% of the human capital development in the country.

Effect of Curriculum Scope on the Human Capital Development

The structural equation model relating to the second objective was formulated as shown in Figure 3. The outer models represent a total of seven surveyed items for scope in curriculum (labelled Q10-Q15) and the seven surveyed items for human capital development (labelled Q26-Q32). The inner model depicts our reflective constructs including having science

subjects and extra-curriculum activities in the education system. We argued that broad coverage in the curriculum help develop the learners in an all-round manner for sustainability in the social and economic development. Hence, scope in the curriculum can cultivate the learner's development to become future human resource drivers. Our results are presented and analysed in Table 5.

Figure 3. Structural Equation Model- Curriculum Scope on HCD
Source: Primary data (2023)

Depicted in Figure 3 is the path diagram showing the structural analysis of between scope in curriculum, as proxied by science subjects and extra-curriculum activities, on the human capital development. The inclusion of science subjects was considered as an approach to broaden the curriculum coverage in the Rwandan context. In addition, extra-curriculum activities provide avenues for learners to integrate other important

fields including the social interactions, environmental responsibility and physical world with an aim to develop learners with sustainability mentality. Consequently, we argued that having a broad curriculum in an education system can enhance human capital development that is imbued with sustainability of the society, environment and economy. The analyses of our results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. PLS-SEM analyses for Scope in Curriculum

Path	Path coefficients	p-values	r	R ²	AdjR ²
Science -> HCD	0.304	0.000	0.472		
Extra-Curriculum -> HCD	0.325	0.006	0.482	0.300	0.2949

Source: Primary data (2023)

Reported in Table 5, the PLS-SEM analyses show that including extra-curriculum activities in the education system contributes positively and significantly to HCD. The path coefficient was 0.325 with correlation ($r=0.482$, $p<0.05$) that was positive and statistically significant. Similarly, having science subjects in the education system positively influences the HCD with path coefficient of 0.304 and correlation of $r=0.472$ ($p<0.05$). The combined effect of these two give the contribution of curriculum scope with $R^2=0.300$, indicating that 30% of the variation in human capital development in Rwanda can be attributed to the curriculum coverage.

Effect of Industrial Matching on Human Capital Development

The structural equation model in relation to objective three was formulated as shown in Figure 4. The outer models represent a total of ten surveyed items for inclusive education (labelled Q16-Q25) and seven surveyed items for human capital development (labelled Q26-Q32). The inner model depicts our reflective constructs with skills development, meeting the market needs and employability of the learners as the constructs measuring the industrial matching in the education system. We argued that for an education system to be relevant, it must match its contents to the industry or the market it serves. With this in mind, it is possible to develop an education system such that human capital is developed to fit seamlessly in the market. Our results are provided in Table 6.

Figure 4. Structural Equation Model- Industrial Matching on HCD

Source: Primary data (2023)

Depicted in Figure 4 is the pictorial presentation of the path from the three reflective constructs of industrial matching to the dependent variable, human capital development. In this study, we argued that industrial matching renders an

education system more relevant to the society and the economy. The learners are developed in such a way that they are easily integrated into the market after their education. Moreover, the purpose of the education is to empower the

learners with skills needed at the market to solve the social, economic and environmental challenges facing the human society. Hence, the need for an education to develop the skills that meet the market needs and empower the learners to be competitive in the labour market. Hence,

we argued that skill development, having an education system that addresses the market needs and that increases the employability of the learners importantly influence the human capital development for sustainable development. Our results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. PLS-SEM Analyses for Industrial Matching

Path	Path coefficients	p-values	r	R ²	AdjR ²
Skills -> HCD	0.279	0.004	0.584		
Market Needs -> HCD	0.207	0.000	0.555	0.452	0.446
Employability -> HCD	0.298	0.000	0.586		

Source: Primary data (2023)

Table 6 reports our findings in relation to the effect of industrial matching to the human capital development. Three reflective constructs included skill development, meeting the market needs and increasing the employability of learners. As per the findings, an education system that increases employability of the learners has the biggest positive contribution with a path coefficient of 0.298 and positive and significant correlation ($r=0.586$, $p<0.000$). This

was closely followed by skill development component with a path coefficient of 0.279 and correlation ($r=0.584$, $p<0.000$) that was statistically significant. Lastly, meeting market needs has a path coefficient of 0.207 with a positive correlation ($r=0.555$, $p<0.000$). The overall contribution shown by $R^2=0.452$ implied that industrial matching in an education system contributes 45.2% of the human capital development in Rwanda.

Table 7. PLS-SEM Overall Analysis for Sustainability Education

Path	Path coefficients	p-values	H ₁ Decision	r	R ²	AdjR ²
Inclusive Education -> HCD	0.205	0.003	Accepted	0.540		
Scope -> HCD	0.111	0.000	Accepted	0.560	0.495	0.489
Industrial Matching -> HCD	0.479	0.029	Accepted	0.673		

Source: Primary data (2023)

Table 7 reports the overall results analysing the effect of sustainability education on the human capital development. As noted earlier, our hypotheses were formulated in respect to our reflective constructs arguing that inclusive

education, curriculum scope and industrial matching have positive impact on the human capital development. The path coefficients were all positive and significant. This implied that all the hypotheses were accepted. Therefore,

inclusive education contributes positively to HCD at 20.5%, curriculum scope at 11.1% and industrial matching at 47.9% as shown by our analyses. Industrial matching has the biggest contribution followed by inclusive education. The need for building a sustainability education that is all inclusive and that matches the industrial needs cannot be ignored. With such an education system, the learners acquire skills and capacities that empower them to be economically, socially and holistically productive for this and future generation. Well-integrated curriculum builds socially responsible human capital, that is not only for their economic benefit, but also for the society at large. In addition, they gain useful knowledge with an open mind that work to utilize, preserve and protect the environment.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The value and the originality of this paper lies on the need to integrate sustainability education for human capital development that is capable of shaping human actions towards constructive coexistence and human-nature relationship. Access to quality education is good for a country. However, this by itself is not sufficient enough. The education system should provide learning opportunities that are more comprehensive, broad enough and that lead to quality human capital readily employable to help meet the labour markets' needs. Further, it should impart knowledge, skills and instil awareness to the learners on social, economic and environmental responsibility for today's and future generation. In that way then, the education system can be seen as sustainability education.

The results of this research should be considered as an invitation for new research initiatives regarding incorporating the new sustainability concerns into the schools' curricula for a better human capital development. Further, to facilitate development of learners in such a way that they appreciate their shared responsibilities to future generation to account and preserve the planet. The study has both practical and policy implications. We recommend that the regulators

in the education to pay closer attention to the curricula offered in schools and particularly in higher learning institutions. There should be subjects that teach learners their social and environmental responsibilities. Curricula developers should also be conscious of the modern day demands for green environment and provide subjects that promote social-economic-environmental balance. Further, educators should embrace practices that may increase learners' knowledge and understanding of their shared responsibilities. Moreover, our human actions have both positive and negative consequences to us, the society, economy and the environment.

References

- Adedeji, O., & Campbell, O. (2013). The role of higher education in human capital development. *Available at SSRN 2380878*.
- Becker, G. S. (1994). Human capital revisited. In *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis with Special Reference to Education*, 3rd ed. (15-28). The University of Chicago Press.
- Care, E., & Anderson, K. (2016). *How education systems approach breadth of skills*. Washington, DC: Centre for Universal Education at Brookings.
- Clark, T., Foster, L., Bryman, A., & Sloan, L. (2021). *Bryman's social research methods*. Oxford University Press.
- Donald, W. E., Ashleigh, M. J., & Baruch, Y. (2018). Students' perceptions of education and employability: Facilitating career transition from higher education into the labour market. *Career development international*, 23(5), 513-540. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-09-2017-0171>
- Engbers, T. A., Thompson, M. F., & Slaper, T. F. (2017). Theory and measurement in social capital research. *Social Indicators Research*, 132, 537-558. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-016-1299-0>
- Fiselier, E. S., Longhurst, J. W., & Gough, G. K. (2017). Exploring the current position of ESD in UK higher education institutions. *International*

Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-06-2017-0084>

Glavic, P. (2020). Identifying key issues of education for sustainable development. *Sustainability*, 12(16), 6500.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su12166500>

Green, M., & Somerville, M. (2015). Sustainability education: Researching practice in primary schools. *Environmental Education Research*, 21(6), 832-845.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2014.923382>

Kola-Olusanya, A. (2013). Embedding environmental sustainability competencies in human capital training and development. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(4), 65.

Leicht, A., Heiss, J., & Byun, W. J. (2018). *Issues and trends in education for sustainable development* (Vol. 5). UNESCO publishing.

Lenglet, F., Fadeeva, Z., & Mochizuki, Y. (2010). ESD promises and challenges: Increasing its relevance. *Global Environment Research*, 14(2), 93-100.

MINEDUC [Ministry of Education] (2020). *MINEDUC Service Charter*. Kigali: Government Publication.

Mundial, G. B., & UNICEF. (2016). *Education 2030: Incheon declaration and framework for action: towards inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning for all*. Paris: UNESCO Publication.

Njoku, J. U., & Onyegbula, J. C. (2017). Human capital development as a strategy for sustainable development in the Nigerian education system. *African Research Review*, 11(2), 178-189.
[10.4314/afrrrev.v11i2.13](https://doi.org/10.4314/afrrrev.v11i2.13)

Nousheen, A., Zai, S. A. Y., Waseem, M., & Khan, S. A. (2020). Education for sustainable development (ESD): Effects of sustainability education on pre-service teachers' attitude towards sustainable development (SD). *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 250, 119537.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119537>

Nsanzimana, D., & Tushabe, R. (2010). *Guidelines for infusing education for sustainable development into schools in Rwanda*. REMA publication: Kigali.

O'Neill, M., & Bagchi-Sen, S. (2023). Public universities and human capital development in the United States. *GeoJournal*, 88(1), 733-751.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-022-10636-1>

Pather, S., & Slee, R. (2018). *Challenging inclusive education policy and practice in Africa*. BRILL.

Quendler, E., & Lamb, M. (2016). Learning as a lifelong process-meeting the challenges of the changing employability landscape: competences, skills and knowledge for sustainable development. *International Journal of Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning*, 26(3), 273-293.

<https://doi.org/10.1504/IJCEELL.2016.078447>

Ringle, C. M., Wende, S., and Becker, J.-M. 2022. *SmartPLS 4*. Oststeinbek: SmartPLS GmbH,
<http://www.smartpls.com>.

Risher, J., & Hair Jr, J. F. (2017). The robustness of PLS across disciplines. *Academy of Business Journal*, 1, 47-55.

Schultz, T. W. (1961). Investment in human capital. *The American economic review*, 51(1), 1-17.

Sharma, U., & Kelly, M. (2014). Students' perceptions of education for sustainable development in the accounting and business curriculum at a business school in New Zealand. *Meditari Accountancy Research*, 22(2), 130-148.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/MEDAR-12-2012-0042>

Storen, L. A., & Aamodt, P. O. (2010). The quality of higher education and employability of graduates. *Quality in Higher Education*, 16(3), 297-313.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13538322.2010.506726>

Tan, W. C. K. (2022). *Research methods: A practical guide for students and researchers*. World Scientific.

UNDP (United Nations Development Programme). 2019. *Human Development Report 2019: Beyond Income, Beyond Averages, Beyond Today*:

Inequalities in Human Development in the 21st Century. New York: UNDP Publication.

UNESCO, (2017). *A guide for ensuring inclusion and equity in education*. Paris: UNESCO Publication.

UNESCO, (2021). *Welcoming learners with disabilities in quality learning environments, A tool to support countries in moving towards inclusive education*. Paris: UNESCO Publication.

Verhulst, E., & Lambrechts, W. (2015). Fostering the incorporation of sustainable development in higher education. Lessons learned from a change management perspective. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 106, 189-204.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.09.049>

Wilson, L. A., & Stevenson, C. N. (Eds.). (2018). *Building Sustainability Through Environmental Education*. IGI Global.